

Competitive Adsorption in Monolayers: Part V. Cl^- , Br^- and I^- Ions on Silver and Aluminium

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Simultaneous adsorption of Cl^- , Br^- , and I^- ions from the aqueous binary mixtures upon silver and aluminium is measured using the radioisotopes ^{131}I , ^{82}Br and ^{36}Cl to label the systems. The uptake of ions is limited to monolayer thickness. Generally the uptake of one halide ion is suppressed in the presence of another, except in the case of I^- ion on silver in the presence of Br^- ion. This is attributed to the primary kinetic salt effect due to the latter. Results are tabulated giving the times needed for monolayer completion by each halide ion, present singly or in different binary mixtures and the relative fractions of the mixed monolayer occupied by either ion.

THE competitive adsorption on silver and aluminium was studied by measuring the rates of completion of a monolayer of the halide ions, when present singly and in a binary mixture. The experimental procedure employed is the same as reported earlier in our work on radiotracer studies of competitive adsorption in multilayers^{1,2}, using ^{131}I , ^{82}Br and ^{36}Cl as tracers.

Two aspects are studied in the present work: (i) the fraction of the monolayer covered by a given halide ion in the presence of another in a binary mixture, initially of equal concentrations of the two ions and (ii) the change in the rate of uptake of a given halide ion due to the presence of the second one.

Table 1 gives the times needed for completing a monolayer by each halide ion when present singly and in different binary mixtures. The table also shows in the latter case the relative fractions of the monolayer occupied by either ion.

In the case of adsorption from binary halide ion mixtures on silver, each ion being initially of concentration $10^{-3} M$, it is observed that:

- (i) The adsorption of I^- ion (a) in the presence of Cl^- ion proceeds as in the case of pure NaI solution while (b) in the presence of Br^- ion the uptake of I^- ion proceeds faster.
- (ii) The adsorption of Br^- ion (a) in the presence of Cl^- ion proceeds as in the case of pure NaBr

TABLE 1—MONOLAYER ADSORPTION ON SILVER AND ALUMINIUM FROM PURE AND MIXED ADSORBATES OF HALIDE IONS EACH OF INITIAL CONC. $10^{-3} M$; $\text{pH} = 3.5$; TEMP. = 30°

	on silver		on aluminium	
	Time needed for the completion of a monolayer wholly by the given ion	% coverage by the given ion when mixed monolayer is completed	Time needed for the completion of a monolayer wholly by the given ion	% coverage by the given ion when mixed monolayer is completed
(i) Adsorption of I^- ion				
(a) singly present	0.23 s	100	18 hr	100
(b) in presence of Cl^- ions	0.23 s	~100	40 hr	13
(c) in presence of Br^- ions	0.17 s	~100	30 hr	44
(ii) Adsorption of Br^- ion				
(a) singly present	2.0 s	100	1 hr	100
(b) in presence of Cl^- ions	15.0 s	~100	70 hr	62
(c) in presence of I^- ions	5 hr	10^{-3}	100 hr	56
(iii) Adsorption of Cl^- ion				
(a) singly present	20 hr	100	100 hr	100
(b) in presence of Br^- ions	200 hr	2×10^{-3}	115 hr	38
(c) in presence of I^- ions	70 hr	4×10^{-5}		0

solution but the rate of uptake is much slower needing 15 s to complete the monolayer instead of 2 s in pure NaBr solution while, (b) in the presence of I⁻ ion the adsorption of Br⁻ ion is nearly wholly suppressed.

(iii) The adsorption of Cl⁻ ion is wholly suppressed in the presence of either Br⁻ or I⁻ ion.

Fig. 1. Competitive adsorption on silver of:
 I⁻ ions from (A) NaI solution —○,
 " " " NaI + NaCl solution —△,
 " " (B) NaI + NaBr solution —●
 Br⁻ ions from (C) NaBr solution —●
 " " (D) NaBr + NaCl solution —⊕
 Cl⁻ ions from (E) NaCl solution —○
 Initial conc. of all ions = 10⁻³M
 pH = 3.5; temp. = 30°.

Fig. 1 shows these results of competitive adsorption. It may be seen that the order of preferential adsorption is $a_{I^-} > a_{Br^-} > a_{Cl^-}$. It may be further noted

from Fig. 1 that the rate of uptake of I⁻ ion is greatly enhanced in the presence of Br⁻ ion not only in the monolayer but also in the extended multilayers³, suggesting that Br⁻ ion has a primary positive salt effect upon the kinetics of adsorption of I⁻ ion on silver.

The results for the competitive adsorption of halide ions on aluminium surface differ markedly from those on silver. The halide films on aluminium have a high solubility with the result that the uptake of halide ions is slow. Results show that in contrast to silver, the extent of adsorption of I⁻, Br⁻ and Cl⁻ ions from binary mixtures are comparable; though the rate of uptake of I⁻ ion is greatly suppressed in the presence of Cl⁻ ion. The order of preferential adsorption on aluminium is found to be $a_{Br^-} > a_{I^-} > a_{Cl^-}$.

The present study reveals in general that, except in the case of the uptake of I⁻ ion on silver in the presence of Br⁻ ion, there is a lowering of the rate of uptake of halide ions during competitive adsorption. These results on the competitive adsorption of labelled ions are similar to those reported by Young and Crowell⁴ in the case of mixed adsorption of gases on solids. The adsorption of each gas decreases in the presence of the other to the extent the other one is adsorbed which they describe as the 'exclusion principle' in mixed adsorption.

References

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